

Three New Species and Two New Records of the Earwig Genus *Mongolabis* Zacher (Dermaptera: Anisolabididae: Anisolabidinae) from Thailand

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Abstract In the present paper *Mongolabis chiangmaiensis* sp. nov. from Chiang Mai Province, *M. chantha* sp. nov. from Chanthaburi Province and *M. siamensis* sp. nov. from Nan Province are described and illustrated. *M. panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko, 1953) from Chiang Mai Province and *M. emarginata* Srivastava, 2003 from Chanthaburi Province are newly recorded for Thailand. A key to the species of *Mongolabis* in Thailand and a preliminary checklist of the world species of the genus *Mongolabis* Zacher are provided. ZooBank LSID: <https://zoobank.org/References/C30E0FD5-2CA9-46FD-BF40-B7E59920C4BF>

Introduction

The genus *Mongolabis* Zacher, 1911 (Anisolabididae, Anisolabidinae) was established for a species from Japan (Kanagawa and Kyoto), and *Gonolabis woodwardi* Burr, 1908 and *G. forcipata* Burr, 1908 from Western Australia. Subsequently, *G. woodwardi* was designated by Burr (1911: 34) as the type species of *Mongolabis*. This genus was synonymized with *Euborellia* by Popham & Brindle (1966) and *Gonolabis* by Steinmann (1979) but was redefined by Srivastava (1999) to include those species having parameres about 1.5 times longer than broad, rectangular in shape, sometimes with an oblique inner margin. Recently, Anisyutkin (2020) amended the diagnosis of this genus as following: parameres (metaparameres in Anisyutkin, 2020) slightly (approximately 1.5 times) longer than wide and having angularly projecting outer margins and attenuated apices. In the present paper, however, we adopted Srivastava's diagnosis (1999, 2003b) of this genus. The genus *Mongolabis* comprises 43 species and is distributed worldwide, 28 of which are distributed in the Oriental Region (Table 1). Only three species hitherto have been recorded from Thailand: *M. cavaleriei* (Borelli, 1921) (as *Gelotolabis cavaleriei* in Srivastava, 1987; *Euborellia cavaleriei* in Srivastava, 1999 and Nishikawa, 2005), *M. affinis* Ramamurthi, 1973 and *M. omei* (Bey-Bienko, 1959) (Ramamurthi, 1973; Srivastava, 1987, 1999; Nishikawa, 2005).

Recently, we found three new species and two unrecorded species of the genus *Mongolabis* in the collection of the Natural History Museum, Thailand, (THNHM). Three new species are described, and two unrecorded species are added to the earwig fauna of Thailand.

Material and Method

The materials used in this study are housed in the collection of the Natural History Museum, Thailand (THNHM). The type materials of the new species are deposited in THNHM. A stereomicroscope (Nikon SMZ1000; Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) and a digital microscope (Shimadzu BA210EINT; Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) were used for morphological observation. The dried specimens were soaked in hot water to soften them, and

the male genitalia were removed from the body. The male genitalia were treated with 5% KOH for one to six hours until softened and cleared. They were washed with distilled water and then transferred to glycerol on a microscopic glass slide. After the observation, the genitalia were transferred to glycerol in a glass or plastic tube ("genital vial" of Bioquip Products, Inc., USA) and attached to the same pin as the specimen. Habitus images were taken using a single-lens reflex camera (Canon EOS Kiss X7) with a macro photo lens (Canon EFS 60 mm Macro USM) and an extension tube (Canon Extension Tube EF25 II), and stacked using Combine ZP software (Hadley, 2010). Digital images for figures were edited by Adobe Photoshop© CS2.

The data for specimens are cited verbatim in the original spelling and given in double quotation marks (""). The single slash (/) separates rows within each label.

The terminology of male genitalia follows by Hincks & Popham (1970) and Kamimura (2014).

Taxonomy

Family Anisolabididae Verhoeff, 1902 sensu Engel & Haas, 2007

Subfamily Anisolabidinae Verhoeff, 1902 sensu Engel & Haas, 2007

Anisolabidinae Verhoeff, 1902. Type genus: *Anisolabis* Fiebel, 1853. – Srivastava, 1999: 80. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 5. – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Gonolabidae Verhoeff, 1902: 186. Type genus: *Gonolabis* Burr, 1900. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 7 (corrected original spelling as Gonolabididae). – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Gonolabidinae Verhoeff, 1902. Type genus: *Gonolabis* Burr, 1900. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 4. – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Psalinae Burr, 1909: 325. Type genus: *Psalis* Audinet-Serville, 1831. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 10. – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Landicinae Burr, 1915: 445. Type genus: *Landex* Burr, 1915. – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Carcinophorinae Popham, 1965: 132. Type genus: *Carcinophora* Scudder, 1876. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 11 (changed authorship and date of the subfamily name from Hincks (1945: 5) to Popham (1965: 132); Carcinophorinae Hincks, 1945, nomen nudum)). – Engel

& Haas, 2007: 10. – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Placolabidinae Srivastava, 1999: 80. Type genus: *Placolabis*
Bey-Bienko, 1959. – Engel & Haas, 2007: 12 (synonymized
with Anisolabidinae). – Hopkins *et al.*, 2023.

Genus *Mongolabis* Zacher, 1911

Mongolabis Zacher, 1911: 385. Type-species: *Gonolabis woodwardi* Burr, 1906 (designated by Burr, 1911: 34). – Burr, 1911: 34; 1915: 544. – Popham & Brindle, 1966: 272 (synonymized with *Euborellia* Burr, 1910). Hebard, 1933: 146 (not to recognize *Mongolabis* as distinct from *Gonolabis*). – Bey-Bienko, 1936: 92, 218 (treated as subgenus of *Anisolabis*) – Townes, 1945: 353. Hincks, 1954: 7. – Ramamurthi, 1973: 13. – Steinmann, 1979: 165 (synonymized with *Gonolabis*); 1989a: 186 (included as synonym of *Gonolabis*); 1989b: 283 (included as synonym of *Gonolabis*). – Sakai, 1982: 25 (treated as subgenus *Euborellia*) – Srivastava, 1999: 84 (diagnosis redefined); 2003a: 69. – Anisyutkin, 2020: 961 [1152] (diagnosis amended). – Anisyutkin & Van Thinh, 2020: 126.

Gelotolabis Zacher, 1911: 385. Type-species: *Gelotolabis burri* Zacher, 1911 (original designation). – Burr, 1915: 536. – Bey-Bienko, 1959: 600 [541] (treated as subgenus of *Anisolabis*) – Townes, 1945: 349. – Popham & Brindle, 1966: 272 (synonymized with *Euborellia* Burr, 1909). – Brindle, 1978: 71 (included as synonym of *Anisolabis*). – Steinmann, 1977: 94; 1979: 165 (synonymized with *Gonolabis*); 1989a: 186 (included as synonym of *Gonolabis*); 1989b: 204 (included as synonym of *Anisolabis*). – Srivastava, 1999: 74, 84 (synonymized with *Mongolabis* Zacher, 1911).

Cerolabis Bey-Bienko, 1959: 607 [546] (treated as subgenus of *Anisolabis*). Type-species: *Anisolabis (Cerolabis) hwangi* Bey-Bienko, 1959 (original designation). – Srivastava, 1976: 27; 1999 (synonymized with *Mongolabis*). – Steinmann, 1989b: 283 (included as synonym of *Gonolabis*).

Paraflexiolabis Steinmann, 1989a: 37. Type-species: *Paraflexiolabis ornata* Steinmann, 1989a (original designation); 1989b: 302. – Srivastava, 1999: 74, 84 (synonymized with *Mongolabis*).

Anisolabis interjacens species group (pars) Anisyutkin, 1998: 631 (*Anisolabis interjacens* Anisyutkin, 1998, *A. incrassatus* Anisyutkin, 1998, *A. incurvatus* Anisyutkin, 1998, *A. fusoides* Anisyutkin, 1998, and *A. dealbatus* Anisyutkin, 1998, were transferred to *Mongolabis* by Anisyutkin (2020: 961 [1152])).

Diagnosis (after Srivastava, 2003a). Male parameres roughly 1.5 times longer than broad, rectangular in shape, sometimes with inner margin oblique. Besides, in most cases, the external apical angle is projecting, and tip is pointed or anteriorly produced to form a sort of snout.

Mongolabis chiangmaiensis Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.

(Figs. 1a, 2a, 3a, 4a)

Type material. Holotype: ♂: “N. THAILAND / Chiang Mai Prov. / Omkoi Dist, Mae Tuen Subdist., HEF”, “18 NOV

2016/W. Jaitrong Leg. / WJT181116-A”.

Description. Male. Length: body (without forceps): 15.0 mm; forceps: 2.4 mm.

General color dark reddish black; antennae greyish yellowish blown, with two basal segments yellowish brown; maxillary palpi yellowish brown; sides of pronotum slightly paler; legs brown, with femora darkened basal two-third; forceps dark reddish brown but lighter than abdominal tergites.

Head almost as long as broad, rugosely punctured; frontal sutures distinct; coronal suture indistinct; frons moderately convex, occiput depressed. Eyes small, almost 1/2 as long as post-ocular length. Antennae 19 (+?) segmented, partly broken (19 segments on right and 16 segments on left remain); 1st stout, expanded apically, shorter than the distance between antennal bases; 2nd short, about as long as broad; 3rd long, almost half length of 1st; 4th short, shorter than 3rd and 5th; 5th shorter than 3rd; 6th about as long as 3rd and remaining gradually increasing in length distally. Pronotum sparsely punctured, broader than long, slightly expanded posteriorly, with sides depressed; lateral margin almost straight and posterior one slightly rounded; median sulcus weak; pro- and metazona feebly differentiated. Tegmina and wings entirely absent. Meso- and metanotum slightly broader than pronotum and similarly sculptured though not quite so strongly; each with a median line corresponding to the median sulcus of the pronotum; metanotum shorter and broader than mesonotum. Prosternum longer than broad, constricted between front-coxae, anterior margin rounded, posterior margin truncate; mesosternum about as long as broad, sides almost straight, posterior margin rounded; metasternum truncate posteriorly. Legs with hind 1st tarsal segment longer than 3rd. Abdomen gradually expanded to 8th tergite thence slightly contracted to ultimate tergite; tergites finely punctured; sides of tergites 6th to 9th (2a) obtuse posteriorly and weakly carinate on 6th to 8th only. Penultimate sternite (3a, 4a) strongly narrowed posteriorly, sides almost straight and oblique, posterior margin almost truncate. Ultimate tergite transverse, slightly narrowed posteriorly; median sulcus moderately distinct; surface rugosely punctured; posterior margin almost truncate. Forceps sub-contiguous at base, trigonal in basal one-third, slightly asymmetrical, right being slightly more abruptly incurved than left; inner margin slightly serrated. Genitalia (5a) with parameres about 1.3 times as long as broad, apex rounded, inner margin slightly sinuate at middle, outer margin obtusely angulate at basal three-fifth; penis lobes with minute transparent teeth; virga indistinct.

Female unknown.

Remarks. This species is similar to *Mongolabis insidiata* (Steinmann, 1979) from Vietnam, but smaller (in male *M. insidiata*, body length with forceps of 28 mm; Steinmann, 1989a); male genitalia with outer margin of paramere obtusely angulate at basal three-fifth, without sclerotized plate in penis lobe (in *M. insidiata*, outer margin of paramere angulate at basal one-third, with a specific sclerotized plate in penis lobe).

Etymology. The specific epithet refers to the type locality, Chiang Mai Province.

Figs. 1. Habitus of male *Mongolabis* spp. – a, *M. chiangmaiensis* sp. nov.; b, *M. chantha* sp. nov.; c, *M. siamensis* sp. nov.; d, *M. panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko); e, *M. emarginata* Srivastava.

Mongolabis chantha Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.
(Figs. 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b)

Type material. Holotype ♂: “22.1.2006, Tab Sai Subdist. / Pong Nam Ron Dist. / Chanthaburi Prov. 1500-1600 msl. /

W. Jaitrong leg.”, “THNHM-I- / 2008-01500”, “I-220108-27”, “Unidentified species / DAN-3174”.

Description. Male. Length: body (without forceps): 17.0 mm; forceps: 3.5 mm.

General color dark reddish black; head reddish brown;

Figs. 2–4. – 2, Sides of male abdominal tergites VI–IX, lateral view; 3, male penultimate sternite and forceps, ventral view; 4, posterior margin of penultimate sternite. – a, *M. chiangmaiensis* sp. nov.; b, *M. chantha* sp. nov.; c, *M. siamensis* sp. nov.; d, *M. panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko); e, *M. emarginata* Srivastava.

antennae greyish yellowish brown, with two basal segments yellow; segment 17 on right and segments 16 and 17 on left slightly lighter in color; maxillary palpi yellowish brown; thoracic nota light reddish brown; sides of pronotum yellowish brown; legs yellowish brown, with femora darkened basally; forceps dark reddish brown but lighter than abdominal tergites.

Head slightly longer than broad, moderately convex, sparsely punctured; sutures defined. Eyes small, almost 1/2 as long as post-ocular length. Antennae 19 (+?) segmented, partly broken (19 segments on right and 18 segments on left remain); 1st stout, expanded apically, shorter than the distance between antennal bases; 2nd short, about as long as broad; 3rd long, slightly longer than the half-length of 1st; 4th short, shorter than 3rd; 5th slightly longer than 4th; 6th about as long as 3rd and remaining gradually increasing in length distally. Pronotum slightly broader than long, expanded posteriorly, with sides depressed; lateral margin almost straight and posterior one almost straight; median sulcus weak; prtozona moderately convex and weakly differentiated from depressed metazona; surface obscurely punctured with shallow rugose. Tegmina and wings entirely absent. Meso- and metanotum slightly broader than pronotum and similarly sculptured though not quite so strongly; each with a median line corresponding

to the median sulcus of the pronotum; metanotum shorter and broader than mesonotum. Prosternum longer than broad, constricted between front-coxae; anterior and posterior margins truncate; mesosternum slightly broader than long, sides almost straight, posterior margin rounded; metasternum truncate posteriorly. Legs with hind 1st tarsal segment longer than 3rd. Abdomen gradually expanded to 7th tergite thence slightly contracted to ultimate tergite; tergites finely punctured; sides of tergites 7th to 9th (2b) acute angulate posteriorly and carinate. Penultimate sternite (3b, 4b) strongly narrowed posteriorly, sides almost straight and oblique, posterior margin almost truncate. Ultimate tergite transverse, slightly narrowed posteriorly, ecarinate, with a tubercle on each side before posterior margin; median sulcus moderately distinct; surface rugosely punctured; posterior margin almost truncate medially. Forceps remote at base, trigonal in basal one-third, asymmetrical, right being more abruptly incurved than left; inner margin serrated. Genitalia (5b) with parameres about 1.3 times as long as broad, apex rounded, inner margin slightly sinuate near base, outer margin with angle strongly prominent; penis lobes with minute teeth on surface and two sclerites, long and short, inside; virga indistinct.

Female unknown.

Remarks. This species is similar to *Mongolabis magna*

Fig. 5. Male genitalia of *Mongolabis* spp. – a, *M. chiangmaiensis* sp. nov.; b, *M. chantha* sp. nov.; c, *M. siamensis* sp. nov.; d, *M. panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko); e, *M. emarginata* Srivastava.

(Bey-Bienko, 1959) from China (Yunnan) in having somewhat identical parameres, but differs in that the penultimate sternite being more strongly narrowed posteriorly and the posterior margin being truncate.

Etymology. The specific epithet refers to the type locality, Chanthaburi, which means the “City of the Moon.” “*Chantha*” means moon in the Thai language.

***Mongolabis siamensis* Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.**
(Figs. 1c, 2c, 3c, 4c)

Type material. Holotype ♂: “3.VII.2008. / Disturbed Area., / near Doi Phu Kha NP, Pua dist. / Nan Prov. / T. Chanthaburi leg.”, “THNHM-I- | 2008-05709”, “I-030708-1”.

Description. Male. Length: body (without forceps): 17.0 mm.; forceps: 3.5 mm.

Table 1. A preliminary checklist of the world species of *Mongolabis* Burr (*Original spelling of specific name was corrected under the ICZN Article 31.2 Gender Agreement.)

Species	Distribution
1 <i>Mongolabis aberrans</i> Borelli, 1932	North Borneo (Mt. Kinabalu)
2 <i>Mongolabis abramovi</i> Anisyutkin, 2023	Vietnam (Lao Cai)
3 <i>Mongolabis acuta</i> Srivastava, 2003b	China (Fujian)
4 <i>Mongolabis affinis</i> Ramamurthi, 1973	Thailand (Chiang Mai)
5 <i>Mongolabis bidens</i> (Steinmann, 1981)	New Guinea
6 <i>Mongolabis blanchardi</i> (Guillon, 1841)	Polynesia
7 <i>Mongolabis bochkovi</i> Anisyutkin, 2020	Vietnam (Cao Bang)
8 <i>Mongolabis brunneri</i> (Dohrn, 1864)	Australia, Tasmania
9 <i>Mongolabis cattienensis</i> Anisyutkin, 2023	Vietnam (Dong Nai)
10 <i>Mongolabis cavaleriei</i> (Borelli, 1921)	China, Vietnam (Quang Binh), Thailand (Chiang Mai)
11 <i>Mongolabis chantha</i> Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.	Thailand (Chanthaburi)
12 <i>Mongolabis cheni</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Yunnan)
13 <i>Mongolabis chiangmaiensis</i> Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.	Thailand (Chiang Mai)
14 <i>Mongolabis dealbata</i> (Anisyutkin, 1998)*	Vietnam (Bachthai)
15 <i>Mongolabis depressa</i> Srivastava, 2003b*	China (Fujian)
16 <i>Mongolabis emarginata</i> Srivastava, 2003b*	Vietnam (Dalat, 1500 m)
17 <i>Mongolabis externa</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Yunnan)
18 <i>Mongolabis fallax</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Sichuan, Yunnan)
19 <i>Mongolabis forcipata</i> (Burr, 1908)	West Australia
20 <i>Mongolabis formosae</i> (Borelli, 1927)	China (Inner Mongolia, Jiangsu, Fujian, Guangxi), Taiwan
21 <i>Mongolabis fukiensis</i> Srivastava, 2003b	China (Fujian)
22 <i>Mongolabis fusoidea</i> (Anisyutkin, 1998)*	Vietnam (Vinh Phu)
23 <i>Mongolabis gilesi</i> (Steinmann, 1981)	Australia
24 <i>Mongolabis hwangi</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Sichuan, Yunnan)
25 <i>Mongolabis incrassata</i> (Anisyutkin, 1998)*	China (Yunnan)
26 <i>Mongolabis incurvata</i> (Anisyutkin, 1998)*	China (Yunnan)
27 <i>Mongolabis infelix</i> (Burr, 1907)	Zambia, Malawi, North Mozambique, Tanzania
28 <i>Mongolabis insidiata</i> (Steinmann, 1979)	Vietnam (Lao Cai)
29 <i>Mongolabis interjacens</i> (Anisyutkin, 1998)	Vietnam (Son La)
30 <i>Mongolabis magna</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Yunnan)
31 <i>Mongolabis omei</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Sichuan), Thailand (Chiang Mai)
32 <i>Mongolabis ornata</i> (Steinmann, 1989)	Hawaii
33 <i>Mongolabis pacifica</i> (Erichson, 1842)	Australia, Polynesia, Sandwich Islands, Hawaii
34 <i>Mongolabis panfilovi</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Gansu, Fujian, Guangxi, Yunnan), Thailand (Chiang Mai)
35 <i>Mongolabis quarens</i> (Burr, 1915)	Congo Republic, Cameroon, Togo, Nigeria, Equatorial Guinea
36 <i>Mongolabis scorpio</i> (Steinmann, 1985)	New Guinea
37 <i>Mongolabis sechuana</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1934)	China (Sichuan, Yunnan)
38 <i>Mongolabis siamensis</i> Nishikawa et Jaitrong, sp. nov.	Thailand (Nan)
39 <i>Mongolabis straeleni</i> (Hincks, .1955)	Congo Republic, Zaire
40 <i>Mongolabis tanganyikae</i> (Brindle, 1964)	Tanzania
41 <i>Mongolabis tasmanica</i> (de Bormans, 1880)	Tasmania, S. Australia
42 <i>Mongolabis undata</i> (Bey-Bienko, 1959)	China (Guangxi, Sichuan, Yunnan)
43 <i>Mongolabis uruguayensis</i> (Brindle, 1971)	Uruguay & Chile
44 <i>Mongolabis vallakadaiensis</i> (Ramamurthi et David, 1973)	South India
45 <i>Mongolabis vitalisi</i> (Burr, 1917)	N. Vietnam
46 <i>Mongolabis woodwardi</i> (Burr, 1908)	West Australia

General color dark reddish black; head reddish brown; antennae unicolor, greyish brown; maxillary palpi yellowish brown; legs yellowish, with femora slightly darkened basally.

Head longer than broad, moderately convex, sparsely

punctured; sutures defined. Eyes small, almost 1/2 as long as post-ocular length. Antennae 16-segmented partly broken (right 12 segments remain); 1st stout, expanded apically, shorter than the distance between antennal bases; 2nd short, slightly

shorter than broad; 3rd long, slightly longer than half length of 1st; 4th short, about half length of 3rd; 5th slightly longer than 4th; 6th about slightly longer than 3rd and remaining gradually increasing in length to 14th; 15th slightly shorter than 14th; 15th slightly shorter than 16th. Pronotum about as long as long, slightly expanded posteriorly, with sides gently reflexed; lateral margin almost straight and posterior one rotundate; median sulcus weak; prozona gently convex and weakly differentiated from depressed metazona; surface sparsely punctured. Tegmina and wings entirely absent. Meso- and metanotum slightly broader than pronotum and similarly sculptured though but not quite so strongly; median line of mesonotum weak, median line of metanotum indistinct; metanotum shorter and broader than mesonotum. Legs with hind 1st tarsal segment longer than 3rd. Abdomen gradually expanded to 7th tergite thence slightly contracted to ultimate tergite; tergites finely punctured; sides of tergites 6th to 8th (2c) acute posteriorly and carinate. Penultimate sternite (3c, 4c) narrowed posteriorly, sides almost straight and oblique, posterior margin broadly and slightly emarginate. Ultimate tergite transverse, slightly narrowed posteriorly, ecarinate, with two or three rows of punctures; median sulcus indistinct; posterior parts shallowly rugose; posterior margin in middle almost truncate. Forceps contiguous, trigonal in basal one-third, slightly asymmetrical, right being more abruptly incurved than left; inner margin serrated. Genitalia (5c) with parameres about 1.3 times as long as broad, apex rounded, inner margin slightly sinuate at middle, outer margin with angle rounded; penis lobes with minute teeth on surface and a sclerotized rod inside; virga indistinct.

Female unknown.

Remarks. This species is similar to *Mongolabis Chiangmaiensis* sp. nov. but is larger and differs in having unicolor antennae and yellowish legs, and broadly and slightly emarginate posterior margin of penultimate sternite.

Etymology. The specific name is an adjective meaning 'of Siam (old name of Thailand)'.

***Mongolabis panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko, 1959)**
(Figs. 1d, 2d, 3d, 4d)

Anisolabis (Gelotolabis) panfilovi Bey-Bienko, 1959 [1960]: 602 [542], figs. 19-20 (type-locality: China (Yunnan); holotype probably in the Institute of Entomology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Peking, China).

Anisolabis panfilovi: Sakai, 1970: 71. Anisyutkin, 1998: 795 [633], fig. 24 (in *Anisolabis interjacens* species group).

Gelotolabis panfilovi: Steinmann, 1975: 156, fig. 15; 1979: 175, fig. 15.

Gonolabis panfilovi: Steinmann, 1979: 175, fig. 15; 1989a: 229, fig. 337; 1989b: 293. – Sakai, 1982: 26.

Mongolabis panfilovi: Srivastava, 1999: 89.

Specimens examined. ♂: "N. Thailand / Chiang Mai Prov. / Muang Dist., Doi Pui / HEF", "18 JULY 2016 / W. Jaitrong leg. / General Coll". ♂: "Ban Khun Wang. / Chiang Mai, N. Thailand / alt. 1,700 m., 10.Nov.2005 / S. Makchay leg.", "THNHM-I- / 2005-02999".

Distribution. China (Gansu, Fujian, Guangxi, Yunnan),

Thailand (new record).

Remarks. The present specimens agree with the original description of the species except that all tibiae are pale, the abdomen lacks lateral tubercles on 3rd and 4th tergites, and the posterior margin of penultimate sternite is concave. It is reported from Thailand for the first time.

***Mongolabis emarginata* Srivastava, 2003,**
nomen correctum
(Figs. 1e, 2e, 3e, 4e)

Mongolabis emarginatus Srivastava, 2003b: 33, figs. 91–94 (type-locality: Vietnam (Dalat, 1500 m.); holotype in B. P. Museum, Hawaii).

Specimens examined. ♂: "19.I.2008 / Sai Khao Subdist. DEF. / Soi Dao dist. / Chanthaburi Prov. / W. Jaitrong leg.", "THNHM-I- / 2008-01398", "I-190108-14". ♂: "19.I.2008. Sai Khao Subdist. DEF. / Soi Dao dist. / Chanthaburi Prov. / W. Jaitrong leg.", "THNHM-I- / 2008-01396", "I-190108-12".

Distribution. Vietnam, Thailand (new record).

Remarks. The above male specimens are having characteristic parameres as fig. 5e and are preferable in this species, but differ from original description of the species in that the abdomen is expanded to 7th tergite thence slightly contracted to ultimate tergite, and the sides of tergites 6th to 7th are carinate. It is reported from Thailand for the first time. Since the gender of the genus *Mongolabis* is feminine, the original specific name "emarginatus" must be changed to "emarginata" (ICZN Article 31.2 Gender Agreement).

Key to the species of *Mongolabis* in Thailand
(based on male)

- 1 (12) Large species, length of body with forceps 20–30 mm.
- 2 (3) Legs unicolor; posterior margin of penultimate sternite broadly emarginate; parameres with outer margin rounded. *M. emarginata* Srivastava
- 3 (2) Legs with femora darkened basally; posterior margin of penultimate sternite truncate, emarginate or concave; parameres with outer margin obtusely or acutely angulate.
- 4 (7) Posterior margin of penultimate sternite narrowly truncate.
- 5 (6) Parameres with outer margin strongly prominent and acutely angulate. *M. chantha* sp. nov.
- 6 (5) Parameres with outer margin not strongly prominent but angulate. *M. omei* (Bey-Bienko)
- 7 (4) Posterior margin of penultimate sternite broadly emarginate or concave.
- 8 (9) Penultimate sternite with faint longitudinal ridges in posterior half in middle. *M. affinis* Ramamurthi
- 9 (8) Penultimate sternite without longitudinal ridges.
- 10 (11) Parameres with outer margin angulate.
..... *M. panfilovi* (Bey-Bienko)
- 11 (10) Parameres with outer margin obtusely angulate.
..... *M. siamensis* sp. nov.
- 12 (1) Smaller species, length of body with forceps 13-18mm.
- 13 (14) Legs unicolor; sides of tergites VI–VIII carinate.
..... *M. cavaleriei* (Borelli)

- 14 (13) Legs with femora darkened basally; sides of tergites VII–VIII weakly carinate. *M. Chiangmaiensis* sp. nov.

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